

Retrospective Histomorphological Study of Lichenoid Dermatitides**Khushi Kumari¹, Nazneen Sulaeman², Radhika Mucharla^{3*}**¹Assocate Professor, Department of Pathology, Gandhi Medical College, Bhopal²Senior Resident, Department of Pathology, Chalmeda Ananda Rao Institute of Medical Sciences, Karimnagar, Telangana State^{3*}Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Government Medical College, Ensanpally, Siddipet. Telangana State

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Dense band-like infiltration at the dermo-epidermal junction and damage to basal cells are hallmarks of lichenoid dermatitis, a very common dermatological condition. Lichen planus is the prototype lesion, but a wide variety of lesions fall under this category. This study set out to investigate the histopathological spectrum of lichenoid tissue reaction conditions as well as the clinicopathological concordance of lichenoid lesions.

Materials and Procedures: In a tertiary care facility, a retrospective study was carried out on all skin biopsy cases that were identified as having lichenoid dermatitis for two years (2020–2022) based on clinical and/or histological diagnoses. From the corresponding case sheets and biopsy reports, demographic information, clinical diagnosis, histological diagnosis, and the various histological features were gathered and placed into an Excel worksheet. To depict the data, frequency and percentages were employed.

Results: Of the 82 patients that were clinically diagnosed as lichenoid dermatitis, 76 instances had a diagnosis that agreed with the histological diagnosis. Nine instances were classified as lesions lacking lichenoid features because there was a discrepancy between the clinical and histological diagnosis. Only the histological investigation revealed the seven cases' lichenoid dermatitis diagnosis; no clinical differential diagnosis of this kind was made. Of the 82 instances that were diagnosed as lichenoid dermatitis, there were two cases of lichen planopilaris, five cases of lichen planus pigmentosus, four cases of hypertrophic lichen planus, three cases of lichenoid dermatitis, and 35 cases of lichen planus. Lichenoid dermatitis was most frequently observed in people aged 40 to 52. Compared to men, females were more frequently impacted.

Conclusion: In conclusion, the prototype lesion of lichenoid dermatitides is lichen planus. Making decisions about the patient's prognosis and treatment approach depends on obtaining a definitive diagnosis of the particular entity among the lichenoid lesions. Together with clinical correlation, which indicates that clinicopathological correlation is the key, histopathological testing is essential for the final diagnosis.

Keywords: Histopathology; Band-Like Infiltration; Lichen Planus; Lichenoid Dermatitis.

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Introduction

In dermatology, lichenoid dermatitis is the most frequently occurring lesion both clinically and histopathologically [1]. Histopathological investigation reveals lichenoid tissue reactions/lichenoid dermatitis as a result of epidermal basal cell injury that sets off a series of events. [1]. Histologically, lichenoid dermatitis is characterized by a dense infiltrate of inflammatory cells at the dermoepidermal (DE) junction that resembles a band, primarily lymphocytes, and epidermal basal cell destruction that manifests as liquefactive, hydropic, and vacuolar degeneration. The epidermis exhibits hyperkeratosis, rete-ridge elongation, acanthosis, and numerous other diverse epidermal characteristics [2,3]. The physical

features of lichenoid dermatitis are observed in numerous skin conditions. Lichen planus is the category's archetypal skin lesion. In India, lichen planus accounts for roughly 0.38% of all dermatological outpatients and is the most prevalent chronic dermatosis lesion [3]. In addition to lichen planus, which is the model for lichenoid tissue reactions, other lichen planus conditions that fall under this category include lupus erythematosus, lichen striatus, keratosis lichenoides chronicus, lichen planopilaris, lichen amyloidosis, and hypertrophic lichen planus. All lichenoid dermatitis shares the histological characteristics of epidermal basal cell destruction and a band-like inflammatory cell infiltrate at the DE junction;

nevertheless, each of the skin conditions in this group has a few unique characteristics that help with a conclusive diagnosis. Most of the time, clinical symptoms aid in the diagnosis; however, a histological test is frequently required for a clear diagnosis, which is crucial for patient care. Our goal in this study was to examine the histomorphological range of lichenoid dermatitis in the local populace.

Aims and Objectives:

The aims of this study were as follows:

1. To investigate the spectrum of histopathological abnormalities associated with lichenoid tissue reaction.
2. To determine whether the lichenoid lesions are clinicopathologically concordant.

Materials and Methods

This investigation was carried out in a tertiary care facility using retrospective methods. The study was conducted on all skin biopsy cases that were diagnosed as lichenoid lesions either clinically or histologically during the two-year period between 2020 and 2022. The approval for the study came from the Institute Ethics Committee (IEC) (Human studies), Gandhi Medical College and Research Institute, Bhopal, with approval number 106/IEC-3/2020. Excluded from the study were cases without appropriate tissue material and clinical information.

The histopathology slides were taken from the filed/archived material, and in the event that any of the slides were faded or damaged, new sections were made from the corresponding paraffin blocks and the histopathological study was repeated. The patient's information and clinical diagnoses were taken from the histopathology request form that was received along with the skin biopsy sample

Both dermal and epidermal alterations were examined as histological characteristics. Hyperkeratosis, parakeratosis, acanthosis, papillomatosis, atrophy, spongiosis, hypergranulosis, rete ridge elongation, and basal cell degeneration are the epidermal abnormalities. Melanin incontinence, inflammatory cell type, and band-like inflammatory cell infiltrate at the DE interface were among the dermal characteristics that were examined. These characteristics led to the final diagnosis of lichenoid dermatitis. A comparison was made between the histopathological and clinical diagnoses.

Analytical statistics: For 85 cases, statistical analysis was done. The information was input and expressed as percentages on a Microsoft Excel sheet. It was calculated what the clinicopathological concordance and discordance were.

Results

During the study period, 82 instances of lichenoid dermatitis with a clinical diagnosis were obtained, 70 of these cases demonstrated that the clinical diagnosis and the histopathological diagnostic agreed, and nine cases disagreed with the clinical diagnosis due to histological findings that did not support it. Furthermore, just on the basis of histological investigation, Furthermore, seven individuals were identified as having lichenoid dermatitis alone through histological analysis. Including these cases, our analysis included 80 cases with diagnoses of lichenoid lesions identified.

Of the 82 cases, 28 (37.7%) and (62.2%) were male. With a male-to-female ratio of 0.9:1, the survey found a preponderance of females. Most lichenoid lesions were observed in individuals aged 40 to 50. In this study, a 5-year-old girl was the youngest patient, and a 65-year-old woman was the oldest. According to the findings of our study, the patients who were most frequently impacted were in their fourth and fifth decades of life, followed by their second and third decades, respectively.

Extensive rete ridges, hyperkeratosis, orthokeratosis, and acanthosis were among the epidermal alterations observed in the histopathological examination. Three types of inflammatory cell infiltrates, as well as pigment incontinence into the dermis, were observed in the dermal features. The first infiltrate looked like a band at the DE interface.

38 of the 82 instances with lichenoid dermatitis were identified as lichenoid dermatides; thus, there was a clinical agreement between the histology and clinical diagnosis. Lichen planus, hypertrophic lichen planus, and lichen sclerosis were the only histology-based diagnoses for the remaining cases. The aforementioned cases have morphea, pityriasis lichenoides chronicus, psoriasis, polymorphous light eruption, and fungal infection as differential diagnosis.

Discussion

A papular skin lesion known as a "lichenoid tissue reaction" is defined as epidermal basal cell injury manifested as degeneration or cell death by apoptosis or necrosis. A range of different disorders are included in lichenoid dermatitis. Lichen planus is the classical prototype of the lichenoid dermatides. In order to determine whether the histomorphological spectrum of lichenoid dermatides in our hospital cases corresponded with the clinical diagnosis, we implemented this investigation.

The results of our investigation were consistent with a study by Priya et al. [4] that similarly revealed a female majority of 62.5%, as 28 out of 88 cases (62.2%) were female. The male-to-female

ratio in the study by Parihar et al. [5] was 0.8:1, which was also the same as in our study. Although the majority of the research indicated a female preponderance, there have been no conclusive explanations for the female preponderance in the literature. The lichenoid lesion autoimmunity hypothesis [10] may account for some of the female predominance. It's important to remember that the female preponderance began with the age groups older than 20. The majority of the patients in the current study were found to be between the ages of 18 and 50, with the majority of cases occurring in the fifth decade of life. These findings are consistent with studies by Banushree et al., and Dixit et al., [2,7] in contrast, studies by Parihar et al. and Gupta et al. found that the majority of cases occurred in the 20 to 40 age group [7,12] Five cases from the pediatric age range were included in our study. This indicates that there is a broad age distribution for lichenoid lesions.

The current study included 82 cases, of which 28 cases (60%) were the single major entity. Since more precise features that may have been classified under a particular lichenoid entity were not possible, this broad-based and generic diagnosis was made only on the basis of lichenoid inflammatory infiltration.

The most common epidermal features observed were acanthosis, hyperkeratosis with elongation of rete ridges, and dense DE interface inflammatory infiltrate in almost all of the cases, with the lymphocyte being the major inflammatory cell (Table). The histopathological features of lichenoid dermatitis are attributed to a T-cell-mediated autoimmune attack of epidermal basal cells; hence, it leads to basal cell damage.

Directions among certain lichenoid lesions: Lichenoid dermatitis is a broad category of illnesses characterized by basal cell destruction and a thick inflammatory infiltrate at the DE junction. Solitary, violaceous, crusty eruptions with lichenoid inflammatory infiltration in the upper dermis and epidermal alterations are the hallmarks of lichenoid keratosis, which can be hard to differentiate from lichen planus. [8] A characteristic of lichen planus that is uncommon in lichenoid keratosis is significant parakeratosis. [9] The infundibulum of the hair follicle and the interfollicular spaces exhibit lichenoid inflammatory infiltrates with noticeable follicular plugging in lichen planopilaris. More vacuolar degeneration of the hair follicle's basal cells is present. [10]

Both genital and extra-genital regions, including the face and limbs, are frequently affected by lichen sclerosis et atrophicus. Histologically, there is homogenization with a lymphohistiocytic inflammatory cell infiltrate in the dermis, along

with epithelial atrophy and thinning. [11] Loss of elastic fibers, primarily in the papillary dermis, causes homogenized patches in lichen sclerosis. This is crucial in distinguishing it from morphea, which is characterized by profound dermal fibrosis and sometimes a thick, band-like inflammatory infiltrate. [12] In our clinicopathological correlation investigation, a subject that was initially identified with Morphea was subsequently determined to have lichen sclerosis upon histopathological analysis.

Because mimickers frequently exist, histopathological investigation is crucial in identifying particular organisms in lichenoid dermatosis. Differentiating between each lichenoid dermatosis is crucial because they all have varied treatment needs and differing prognoses. Even though hypertrophic lichen planus is a variety of lichen planus, it should be distinguished from it because long-term instances of hypertrophic lichen planus carry a risk of malignant transition to squamous cell carcinoma, necessitating routine follow-up. [13]

The 80.85% clinicopathological concordance found in our analysis was comparable to the 82% concordance found in the study by Kumar et al. Six Significantly greater concordance percentages of 87.41% and 86%, respectively, were reported by Dixit et al. and Batchu et al. [14], The study by Kumar et al. found 21.50% discordance, which was similar to the few cases (19.67%) that demonstrated discordance with clinical and histological diagnosis, despite the higher concordance rate. Six Poor clinicopathological correlation may be the cause of this discordance, and in certain cases, it may be difficult to get a clinical diagnosis.

Histopathological testing is essential to making a conclusive diagnosis in all those difficult cases. In our investigation, seven cases were identified as having lichenoid dermatitis by histological analysis after the condition had not been included in the clinical differential diagnosis. Thus, in addition to clinical correlation, histological testing is crucial in the diagnosis of particular entities of lichenoid dermatitis.

Because our investigation was retrospective in nature, the clinical association proved to be challenging. As it was a retrospective study, only a small number of cases were discarded because of damaged slides and blocks. We lowered our sample size in part because of this. The minimal sample size in our investigation limited the spectrum of lichenoid dermatitis entities. The restrictions on our study were listed above.

Conclusion

Lichen planus is the most prevalent type of lichenoid dermatitis, which encompasses a wide

range of lesions. A precise identification of the lesion is crucial since different entities require different treatment strategies and outcomes. Histopathological analysis is frequently used to reach a definitive diagnosis. When there are disparities in the clinical details that are available, it leads to clinicopathological discordance. A pathological examination's ability to make a conclusive diagnosis also depends on the clinician's clinical data. The most important way to diagnose lichenoid dermatosis is by histopathological examination, which also helps in prognosticating long-term patient outcomes and selecting the proper course of treatment.

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